

Integrating The Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) and The Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) Strategy to Enhance Students' Reading Comprehension of Descriptive Text in Senior High School

Nadya Oktarima Kusuma Ningtyas¹, Patuan Raja², Flora³

¹ Student of Master of English Education, University of Lampung, Indonesia

^{2,3} Professor of English Education, University of Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to find out whether there is any significant improvement in students' reading comprehension after the students were taught through the integrated Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) and Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) strategy. This is a quasi-experimental research design that conducts a quantitative method with 30 students as the samples. The students were tested through the reading test before and after the treatment namely the integrated DRTA with SQ3R. The data were statistically analyzed using paired samples t-test through SPSS version 22. The finding shows that there is a significant improvement in students' reading comprehension after the students are taught using the integrated Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) and Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) strategy. The average score in the pre-test is 54.33, while in the post-test, it is 72.53. The sig (2-tailed) is 0.000 which is lower than 0.05. It means that there is a significant difference between the score of pre-test and post-test. Then, it is suggested for teachers to apply this new integrated strategy at class because this is a very good choice to embrace students to the effective steps in answering the questions of reading comprehension. Last, this research could be a reference for further researchers who want to conduct similar researches.

KEYWORDS: Directed Reading Thinking Activity, Descriptive Text, Integrating DRTA and SQ3R, Reading Comprehension, Survey Question Read Recite Review.

INTRODUCTION

There are some problems at the tenth graders in reading, including: The first, the most common difficulties in learning English is the lack of the students' interest in learning since the methods used by the teacher did not appeal to the students, which led to a lack of interaction in the classroom, learning environment unpleasant and ineffective. The second, the students are difficult to understand detailed information in the text since it contains a lot of difficult words. So, they would difficult to understand the text and the result, the learning process would be blocked. The third, the students did not have background knowledge required for the reading materials. The factors come from the strategies or methods that are used by the teachers in teaching and learning process, which is the conventional one. The teaching activities only involve listening to teacher's explanation, making lists of difficult words, translating English text into first language, asking students to read loudly or silently, and getting students to answer questions which were related to the text. The teaching and learning process was still traditional approach or teacher-centered.

In this case, the teacher should make variations and choose a suitable method in teaching reading in order to make them interested so that they can improve their perspective towards English language learning especially learning reading comprehension. There were many kinds of teaching methods in English teaching. Therefore for this purpose, learning reading comprehension by using the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) strategy can be one of the alternative to be used in teaching reading comprehension learning process. DRTA extends reading to higher-order thought processes and provide teachers with a great deal about each student's ideas, thought processes, prior knowledge, and thinking skills (Tankersley, 2005). Yadzani and Mohammadi (2015), Aghdam and Behroozizad (2018), Chaemsai and Rattanavich (2016) also have done researches about DRTA. Their researches show that DRTA strategies help the students improve their ability to read and comprehend the text easily.

Although previous studies related to the use of Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method in reading comprehension have been conducted by Mansyah (2014), Utami and Surigin (2019), they believe that Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) has lack a structured approach to guide readers through the text comprehensively, it primarily focuses on predicting, confirming, and modifying predictions, potentially leaving out systematic strategies for understanding the material. Therefore, a more structured approach is needed for further research to explore the potential benefits of a more structured approach to DRTA.

To overcome this problem, the researcher assumed that integrating DRTA (Directed Reading Thinking Activity) with SQ3R (Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Review) could make the method more structured. The founder of the SQ3R strategy is Robinson in 1941. SQ3R is one of the reading strategies which provides students with a systematic and structured approach presenting a detailed step-by-step outline of what readers should complete and accomplish while reading (Robinson, 1961). Further, SQ3R was a comprehension strategy to help students think about the text they were reading (Huda, 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Miller (2002), reading comprehension is not just merely about answering literal questions after reading the text, rather much more beyond such activity. Moreover, Mikulecky and Jeffries (1996) assert that comprehending the text what you read means connecting your prior knowledge with the ideas presented in the text, rather just recognising and understanding words. In other words, reading comprehension goes far beyond the ability to answer questions about factual information, recognise words, accurately read the text aloud, and the like. Comprehension rather involves how to make sense of texts and connect various types of background knowledge (schemata) and reading skills to the ideas of the texts. Besides, according to Nuttall (1982), there are five aspects of reading that the students should understand to comprehend the text well. They are: 1) the main idea, 2) specific information, 3) reference, 4) inference, 5) vocabulary. These aspects are important to comprehend in an English text.

Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is a reading comprehension strategy that is used in each of the three stages of reading (pre-reading, during reading, and post-reading) (Clark and Ganschow, 1995). It emphasizes prediction (thinking ahead), verification (confirmation), and reading with a purpose. The Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is a comprehension strategy that is used to guide students to ask questions about a text and make predictions during reading. They then start to read to find out if their prediction was accurate or not. This can be achieved alone, in a small community or as a whole class. The teacher would usually read the passage to the students, and make them do the part of thinking and predicting. These assumptions and confirmations (or revisions) guide the interpretation of the story by the students (Jennings, Caldwell, and Lerner, 2014). According to Wiesendanger (2001), DRTA allows the students to be active readers. DRTA helps to add new content. It can be used with the basal file, too. Erliyana (2011) conducted a study about DRTA and concluded that the DRTA not only improved students' comprehension but also increased their motivation in learning.

The SQ3R strategy provides a structured approach for students. This strategy has proven to be effective and can easily be integrated into many content areas with a variety of types of text and across grade levels. It is a strategy that students may use throughout the reading process. Using this strategy, students first preview texts to make predictions and generate questions to help direct their reading. As students read, they actively search for answers to their questions, and, when they have finished reading, they summarize what they have read and review their notes, thus monitoring and evaluating their comprehension (Robinson, 1961). Further, SQ3R was a comprehension strategy to help students think about the text they were reading (Huda, 2016). Often categorized as a learning strategy, SQ3R helps students get something from the first time they read the text. Sugiharti (2020) concludes that SQ3R is an excellent reading method for reading comprehension purposes. The purpose of the SQ3R method itself is to increase reader engagement with the reading material they are reading. It can also make the reader search for all the information to answer questions about the content of the reading. This method can also help readers to create a frame of mind so that they can understand whatever they are reading. The activities in SQ3R learning will focus on a structured framework for reading comprehension (Pribadi, 2013). In addition, Masruroh (2015) found that SQ3R helped the students in reading English texts. Therefore, SQ3R is recommended to be implemented in teaching reading comprehension.

In integrating DRTA with SQ3R strategy, the procedures of the DRTA strategy proposed by Clark and Ganschow (1995) are expanded with the stages by Nuttall (1982). Thus, the activities that consist of integrating DRTA with SQ3R strategy become as follows:

Table 1. Activities of Integrating DRTA with SQ3R Strategy

No.	Activity	Origin
1	(Introduction) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher asks some questions to activates students’ schemata The teacher introduces the students about the reading material. 	DRTA
	(Pre-reading Activities) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher encourages students to make initial predictions based on this survey to preview the text, examining titles, headings, and any other fitures that stand out. 	SQ3R
2	(Setting a Purpose) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Before reading the text, the teacher asks the students in a brief discussion about their expectations and predictions based on the survey. The teacher asks the students to make questions related to their survey of the title, headings, and illustrations to activate prior knowledge and stimulate curiosity. 	DRTA + SQ3R
3	(Predictions) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher encourages students to write down these questions of predictions and discuss them in pairs or small groups. 	DRTA
4	(Reading in Chunks) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher asks the students to read a portion of the text using the SQ3R method (Read) to answers their questions of survey predictions in mind. After reading a section, the teacher asks the students pause at key points to discuss predictions, confirmations, with initial expectations. 	DRTA + SQ3R
5	(Discussion and Confirmation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher facilitates a classroom discussion where students share their thoughts, questions, answers of the question and any new predictions based on what they have read in their own words. The teacher encourages students to confirm or revise their predictions based on the text and their understanding 	DRTA + SQ3R
6	(Recitation and review) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher asks students summarize the main points of the section they have read in groups. The teacher encourages students to review their summaries, making sure they align with accuracy of predictions about the entire text and discuss how understanding evolved throughout the reading. 	DRTA + SQ3R

METHODOLOGY

To answer the formulated research question, the researcher conducted a quantitative study in the form of One-group Pretest and Posttest Design.

The researcher gave a pre-test of reading text to the students before treatments, then after treatments the students were given a post-test of reading text. The implementation of the integrated DRTA with SQ3R was applied in three treatments.

PARTICIPANTS

The researcher chose the subjects of the first graders of SMAN 2 Natar because in that school there is no priority class and easier to apply the method. The subjects determined by using purposive sampling technique.

INSTRUMENTS

The students were required to answer the questions of the text as a pre-test and post-test. The students had 50 minutes to do the reading comprehension. The result was then computed through SPSS version 22. The composition of the test is based on the aspects of reading by Nuttal (1982) in order to have construct validity. There are five of sort reading skills, i.e. determining main idea, finding detail information, reference, inference and vocabulary mastery. This research uses split-half method to find the reliability. Below is the result of the split-half method for the reading test:

Table 2. Split-Half

Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	1.000
		N of Items	1 ^a
	Part 2	Value	1.000
		N of Items	1 ^b
	Total N of Items		2
Correlation Between Forms			.919
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		.958
	Unequal Length		.958
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			.957

- a. The items are: Pre-test
- b. The items are: Post-test

Based on the table above, the Guttman Split-Half Coefficient is 0.957. Therefore, it can be concluded that the reading test is reliable.

DATA ANALYSIS

To answer the first research question, the data was analyzed through the paired sample t-test. The researcher then interpreted, described and drew conclusion through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research question is : 'Is there any significant improvement in students' reading comprehension after the students are taught through the integrated Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) and Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) strategy?'. The researcher calculated the data of the post-test and pre-test.

The table below describes the average score of the reading test.

Table 3. Mean Scores of Pre-test and Post-test

Mean	
Pre-test	Post-test
54.33	72.53

From the data above, the mean score of the post-test (72.53) is higher than the pre-test (54.33). To prove the results more accurately, the data were through the paired sample T-test to seek whether there is a significant improvement. The following tables are the result of the Paired Sample T-Test.

Tables 4. Paired Sample T-Test

	Paired Differences	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)					
					Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Pair 1 Post-test - Pre-test	17.93333	1.77984	.32495	17.26873	18.59794	55.188	29	.000	

From the table above, the post-test and the pre-test are compared. The mean score of the post-test is 72.267, whereas it is 54.333 for the pre-test. This indicates that the post-test score is higher than the pre-test score. The mean difference between the post-test and pre-test is 17.933. The t-value is 55.188 at the significant level of 0.000, which is lower than 0.05. It can be concluded that there is a significant increase in the post-test towards the pre-test. The hypothesis (H_1) is then accepted. Equally, it proves that integrating Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) with Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) strategy is able to enhance students' reading comprehension.

The improvement of reading skill occurred because the method was integrated with a strategy that complete the weakness of the original method. It effectively engaged students in class, resulting in more correct answers to questions and overall positive effects on their reading comprehension. Through this new strategy, students not only focus on answering the answer, but more than that, they know how to grasp the key and information provided in the text. They got much new knowledge by reading the text.

Moreover, the students also worked together with their groups discussing the texts, providing feedback, and sharing experiences. The analysis demonstrates that the integrated strategy encouraged students to work together and find the answers effectively. The students gradually comprehend the text's content through a process that started with the activation of past knowledge, progressed to predictions of what they would learn about the subject, and ended with proof. Following those actions, the students will practice correctly understanding the text.

Additionally, Aziz (2020) concluded that Survey (investigate) in a reading activity, especially in using the SQ3R method, there must be a reading survey or material that will be read first. Because with the survey in advance, students can find out which ones are important topics and which ones are only complementary. Next, Question in this method is that students are asked with questions if there are people who have not understood the lessons that have been looked at, and only just maybe just asking only the description of the reading that was read earlier. As to what is the purpose of the title of the lesson. Then, Read in this strategy means that the reading that was already in the reader's mind, by reading, the reader becomes more familiar with the material or reading that was read earlier, and in the end, the question will be answered correctly and done actively. Also, Recite is retelling in reading activities in a way to get further students' memory and understanding. The retelling of this reading can be a story with itself or can be told by a friend. Lastly, Review ask students to review all the questions and answers briefly.

Through all the steps of individual and group works, in conclusion, integrating Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) with Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) strategy is able to enhance Reading Comprehension. Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) has lack of a structured approach to guide readers through the text comprehensively, it primarily focuses on predicting, confirming, and modifying predictions, potentially leaving out systematic strategies for understanding the material. But by looking at the results, the novelty of this research has successfully been proven right where the weakness of the original DRTA was covered by the SQ3R in which the process of the strategy provides a structured approach for students that made them effective in comprehending the reading texts.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The students followed the learning process with the integrated method, i.e. the integrated DRTA with SQ3R strategy. It brings positive impact in enhancing students' reading comprehension. It statistically proves that there is a significant increase in the post-test compared to the pre-test where the type of text was descriptive text. The SQ3R strategy successfully covers the weakness of the original DRTA. Moreover, the students felt more understanding the materials, especially in locating references. They develop their reading aspects. Finally, they increase their achievement of reading comprehension, especially in descriptive text.

Implementing the integration of DRTA and SQ3R in classrooms is a great choice to enhance students' reading comprehension. This strategy engages students not only to read and answer the questions, but also to know the steps of how to grasp the answers effectively. Additionally, teachers may broaden up the students' knowledge with various topic of descriptive text to enrich the learning experience and promote meaningful knowledge. But, in fact, it needs more time to apply this integrated method at class where the teaching hours for studying English in Indonesia are still categorized as few. So teachers had better maintain effective classroom management strategies, particularly during group discussions, to ensure all students have opportunities to participate effectively.

Since this research was conducted only in a certain condition of one of Senior High School in Lampung, namely SMAN 2 Natar, the results of this current research cannot be generalized. But, it could be a reference for further researchers who want to conduct similar research. There are different levels of reading comprehension for each student. It is suggested to the further researchers to differentiate the methods of teaching students with different materials based on the levels of students.

REFERENCES

1. Aziz, I.N. (2020). Implementation Of SQ3R Method In Improving The Students' Basic Reading Skill. *EDUCATION : Journal Of Education*, Volume 5 , Number 1, May 2020.
2. Clark, M.J. and Ganschow, L. (1995). Six reading strategies for adult educators. *Copyright 1995 Ohio Dept. of Education*.
3. Erliana, S. (2011). IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH DIRECTED READING-THINKING ACTIVITY (DRTA) STRATEGY. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, Volume 1, Number 1, March 2011
4. Huda, M. (2016). Model-model pengajaran dan pembelajaran. *Yogyakarta: Pustaka Belajar*.
5. Mansyah, N. (2014). DRTA: A Strategy For Integrating Reading Purpose and Critical Thinking of Students in Reading Text. *Retain : Journal Of Research in English Language Teaching*, 2(3). Retrieved From <https://ejournal.unesa.ac.id/index.php/retain/article/view/9257>
6. Masruroh, M.S. (2015). SQ3R IMPLEMENTATION IN TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION A Case Study of Eight Grade Students at One State MTs in Sumedang. *Journal of English and Education*, 2015, 3(1), 106-121
7. Mikulecky, B. S., and Jeffries, L. (1996). *More reading power*. USA: Addison Wesley Publishing Company, Inc.
8. Miller, D. (2002). *Reading with meaning: teaching comprehension in the primary grades*. USA: Sternhouse Publishers. New York: Random House, Inc.
9. Nuttall, C. (1982). *Teaching reading skills in a foreign language*. Oxford: Heninemann publishers.
10. Pribadi. (2013). Using SQ3R Reading Strategy to Improve Reading Comprehension of Tenth Graders at SMA Negeri 1 Srengat. *Thesis Malang: PPs UNEM*.
11. Robinson, F. P. (1961). *Effective study*. United States: Harper & Row Publisher.
12. Santoso, Singih. (2012). *Statistik Parametrik*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Umum.

13. Sugiharti, R.E., Pramintari, R.D. and Destianingsih, I (2020). SQ3R Method as A Solution To Improve Reading Comprehension Skills in Elementary School. *Indonesian Journal of Primary Education* – Vol .4, No. 2 (2020) 238-24
14. Tankersley, K. (2005). Literacy strategies for grades 4-12: reinforcing the threads of reading. *Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development*.
15. Utami, Y. P., and Surigin. (2019). Fostering students' reading comprehension ability through Directed Reading Thinking Activities (DRTA) strategy. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics*, 4(2), 129-141.
16. Wiesendanger, Katherine D. (2001). *Strategies for Literacy Education*. Columbus: Upper Saddle River

Cite this Article: Nadya Oktarima Kusuma Ningtyas, Patuan Raja, Flora (2024). Integrating The Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) and The Survey, Question, Read, Recite and Reviews (SQ3R) Strategy to Enhance Students' Reading Comprehension of Descriptive Text in Senior High School. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(10), 7980-7986, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i10-58>